

RESEARCH PROJECTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: SKILLS DEVELOPMENT AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Annotation. *The purpose of the work is to show the importance of project work in teaching English, identify the main features and spectrum, describe the influence of students on the learning process and help in language learning. The issue of using project work is of great importance for teaching English. The work of the project is defined as one of the most effective methods of teaching and teaching a foreign language through research and communication, this approach allows it to be applied to all areas of the educational process. It focuses on topics of interest, not specific language tasks, and has interdisciplinary activities that help develop students' thoughts and creativity. However, due to the lack of this method, teachers are not interested in the idea of presenting project work in the classroom. It is believed that the main points of the project work are based on the training of students through research activities and the realization of their interests. The theme of the pedagogical profession is the process of teaching and teaching foreign languages through project work.*

Keywords: *english language teaching, interdisciplinary approach, project-based learning.*

The main focus of this thesis is on teaching English, rather than project work in education. The work of the project is universal, i.e. a standard learning method that can be applied regardless of the topic, context, or purpose of the project.

However, subjects such as physics, chemistry, technical education, etc., often presents the topic through projects other than art in language.

Furthermore, the fact that technical discipline is related to working with tools, tools, tools, testing etc. it is considered "logical" or "natural". However, it is no longer necessary to say that there is a lot of time to learn a language through the project, because language is the most common and effective way of communication. Therefore, Language teachers need to think outside the box and understand the possibilities of learning new, creative, problem-based and project-based languages. Unfortunately, the language curriculum is still based on widely accepted methods and methods. For example, Language Teaching is still largely dependent on grammar and translation methods. Language learning should not be restricted to metric languages by grammar analysis. Literary texts can only be made in a traditional way, where the text is considered to be isolated, away from real life, only in abstract literary terms and the world of fiction.

The project is a work that extends to specific topics, content and presentations that are predominantly defined by students. A teacher or textbook presents a topic, but the author of the project himself decides what to write and how to present it. This quality focused on students in project work is very important, as we will see now as we examine the benefits of project work. Implementing a new approach is not always easy, so we need to make sure that the effort is worth it. English is not considered a household affair by students, but it is a way of communication and pleasure. They can try out not only things in the book, but also real things. The work of the project reflects the three main elements in a better way of communication than any other movement. This is: a) concerns about the motivation, i.e. the attitude of the student to the task. (B) the importance, i.e. the concern about the interaction of language learners. c) concerns about educational values, i.e. the relationship of language curriculum to the overall development of student.

There are a number of interrelated concepts that rely heavily on practical learning principles focusing on everyday reality as a major source of awareness

and ultimate educational goals. These include learning through experience, pragmatism, construction, project-based learning (pbl), and job-based learning/problem-solving.

Learning is related to the methodology through experience. The project approach is "a natural extension of what is already happening in the classroom" (Stoller, 2002, p.109), an open learning process, its limitations and processes are not explicitly defined, which develops in relation to the context of special education and the needs of students and their interests (Frey, 1986; Kriwas, 2007).

The project approach derives from pragmatism, the philosophical movement that emerged in the mid-19th century and promotes the movement and practice of knowledge in everyday life (Frey, 1986, p.31). The main proponent of pragmatism is J. Dewey (1935) and W. Kilpatrick (1935) in the United States, and h. Gaudig et al. kerschensteiner in Germany. The implementation of the project approach was based on the following pedagogical principles, stated by many advanced educators (Chrysafidis, 2005): a) promotion of craft rather than memory and verbalism, b) active participation in the student learning process, and c) exploitation of facts related to immediate reality as a learning resource.

We can also consider the similarities between pbl and CLT language learning. Recently, it has been recognized and accepted as a method that can better respond to the needs of 21st century students than other previously developed methods such as grammar translation, Audiolinguisic methods and direct methods (Kelch, K., 2011) the CLT.). A major difference is the CLT'S focus on developing communication skills, using language learning as a basic tool. This makes Language Teaching and learning a tool to end, not a goal. (Kelch, K.(2011) Everything Is Meaningless.

The topic of the teaching profession is the process of learning and teaching foreign languages through project work. The focus of the research is the work of the project. The objectives of the study are as follows: determining the characteristics of the project's work, defining the types of projects and analyzing the advantages and features, analyzing the organization of the project's work. Basic

research in this field has been carried out by notable scientists and methodologists such as Legutke m., Thomas h., hines S., Brumfit s., hutchinson P., Friedbout d. and others. In his book "Process and Practice in the Language Classroom", Legutke and Thomas present and analyze three types of projects: a meeting project that allows students to interact with native speakers; a written project that encourages students to use English text to analyze a topic or further study the same text, e.g., toys for reading, discussion, dramatizations and practice; an extracurricular project for exchange between students in different countries.

The most obvious point to discuss about the work of the project is that the language is only part of the overall project. Therefore, assessing a project based solely on language accuracy is not very good. It is necessary to honor the overall impact of the project, the level of creativity, accuracy and lightness of its presentation, as well as all the efforts spent on its creation. There is nothing special about it. When evaluating creative writing, evaluating the style etc. it is a common practice. Many educational systems require examination of similar factors when evaluating the effectiveness of oral students in the classroom. Therefore, it is necessary to assess a free "profile" that will assess the entire project.

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